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The Moroccan family between social transition and values

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Abstract:

The system of values in the Moroccan modern society has undergone several changes that affected the individuals and shaped their behavior. The transition between the community society and the individual one led to a couple of transformations in terms of norms, values and status. Thus, instead of adapting ancestors' inherited moral and religious standards, new individual values are put together as a reaction to these tough changes. Through qualitative techniques of data gathering, we have managed to interview a couple of family members in two different areas, the samples were taken from the rural region of 'Souss Massa' and the urban region of Casablanca. The results have exposed that children who have undergone a contemporary familiarization with individual values characterized by building self-confidence, freedom, rationality and pragmatism, are taking the elementary family as a responsible and the whole individual society as a superintendent for many social problems they suffer from: (gender inequality, joblessness, addiction, school dropout...) their argument claims that they have been raised with too much freedom to handle at an early age, and that they weren't capable of making the reasonable choices, meanwhile the current social context was too hard to deal with throughout their life experience. Our interpretation links between the impact of the modern values on children and their tendency to misuse the high degree of uncontrolled freedom. These two facts are potential elements to the understanding of the operating mode of the Moroccan family.

Keywords: Values, Community ,Individual society, Elementary family.